

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Attitude of mass communication trainees of Joseph Ayodele Babalola University (JABU) and Adeyemi College of Education (ACE) towards journalism as a career

BISODUN JOSEPH ADINLEWA *

Department of mass communication, faculty of communication, Adeyemi college of Education Ondo, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study is aimed at examining the attitude of mass communication trainees of Joseph Ayo Babalola University (JABU) and Adeyemi College of Education (ACE) towards journalism as a career. The perception and social cognitive theories were used as theoretical foundation. The researcher adopted purposive sampling technique and as a result; a total number of 347 respondents filled the questionnaire 110 (JABU Mass communication trainees) and 237 (ACE Mass communication trainees). Findings revealed that Mass communication trainees chose to study the course due to their personal decision but majority of them do not want to choose journalism as a career. The study recommends that school management and department board should introduce more practical oriented courses to mass communication curriculum, Government should not interfere in the activities of journalists, and Career journalists should discharge their duties without fear or favor.

Keywords: Mass Communication; Trainee; Career; Journalism; Attitude

1. Introduction

Journalism arguably is a profession that is most widely sought after across the world. While it has been discovered also that most females prefer studying journalism as a course, the same cannot be said of them making career in the profession after graduation. Apke (2016) cited in Patricia, Samuel, Calusa, Fisayo, Ifeoluwa and Omolayo (2015) states that since the inception of journalism as an area of specialization in mass communication studies among Nigerian universities in the 1960s, enrollments have been largely populated by female students. However, further studies have equally revealed that only very few female students usually venture into the practice of journalism after graduation.

Journalism is the collection, preparation and distribution of news, related commentary and feature materials through the media such as pamphlets, newsletters, magazines, radio, television, billboards, internet and books. Journalism as a profession is an essential part of the society. Apart from news and information dissemination, it involves going extra miles in getting news worthy information by way of investigative and interpretative journalism in order to bring out hidden facts and information through the media to the people (Ali, 2010). Okoro and Chiweobo – Onuoha (2013) define journalism as a veritable tool for information dissemination, social mobilization and control. A means of educating the society and sensitizing them on very important issues affecting the lives of the people.

Historically, journalism as a course of study started in Nigeria in the early 1960s, with only two Federal Universities offering courses in journalism. While University of Nigeria, Nsukka started in 1961, the University of Lagos, commercial these programmes in 1967 with the introduction of Diploma in Mass Communication which allowed students to take courses in journalism. Presently, almost all higher institutions of learning in Nigeria offer mass communication courses leading to the award of various degrees and certificates and well as diplomas at National and Higher levels up to

* Corresponding author: ADINLEWA BISODUN JOSEPH

Bachelor and Masters and Ph.D Degrees level. This is in a sharp contrast to what it used to be when candidates were reluctant to enroll in journalism as the preferred career choice as against courses such as Medicine, Accounting, Law and Architecture.

Journalism is a very important institution in every society. It is the practice of investigating and reporting newsworthy events of human interest as they occur through the mass media. Journalists can be said to mirror the society through their reports and discourse of issues which span from diverse areas of the policy (Chioma, 2015).

In contribution, Okoro and Chinweobo-Onuoha (2013) as cited in Chioma (2015) defines journalism to be “a veritable tool for information dissemination, social mobilization, and control. It is a means of public education and sensitization on important issues affecting the lives of the people”. This means that Journalism is the collection, preparation and distribution of news and related commentary and feature materials through such media as a pamphlet, newsletter, magazines, radio, motion pictures, television, Bill Boards, the internet and Books (Ali, 2010).

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Journalism arguably is a profession that is most widely sought after across the world. While it has been discovered also that most female prefer studying journalism as a course, the same cannot be said of them making career in the profession after graduation while more men take it as a profession. Apuke (2016) cited in Patricia, Samuel, Celuwa, Fisayo, Ifeoluwa and Omolayo (2015) states that since the inception of journalism as an area of specialization in mass communication studies among Nigerian universities in the 1960s, enrollments have been largely populated by female students. However, further studies have equally revealed that only very few female students usually venture into the practice of journalism after graduation.

Although there are far more female students in the discipline of mass communication, studies have revealed that only a few of these ladies become journalists. Ali (2010p.5) submit that

Almost all institution of higher learning in Nigeria offers mass communication courses leading to the award of various degrees and certificates, including National Diploma, higher National Diploma, Bachelor, and Masters Degrees. The increase in the number of female graduates from all these Institutions is not reflected in the media of communication in the country. Each Year, hundreds of female students graduate as mass communicators. A close look shows that the number of female Journalists students surpassed the number of males. But in the field today, a good number of these female graduates are not seen working in the various media houses scattered all over the country

Scholars of all stripes have examined the status of women in journalism through the prisms of their own disciplines, from historians documenting the careers of pioneers to cultural studies experts theorizing about how women tweet (McCluskey, 2011) in (Rauhala, and Lindgren 2012). In addition, Sociologists and communication scholars have measured the gender gap in newsrooms and investigated the media’s reinforcement of stereotypes. Researchers have gathered data on content, extracting meaning from clippings and video by counting bylines or conducting interviews. As in so many areas, the multidisciplinary of journalism scholarship, while enriching, mixes methodologies and confounds efforts to summarize findings and generalize themes (Rauhala and Lindgren 2012)

Most of these scholars have found out that there is a high rate of enrolment into journalism as a study and not as a profession. This implies that women love to study communication courses in tertiary institutions but do not wish to

practice the profession, while more men love it as a profession. This could be due to fear, stereotyping, the attitude of people towards women as journalists or even husband's decision on the female journalist.

1.1. Overview of Journalism and Journalism Profession

Over the years, journalism as a profession has been seen as men's job due to its dominance by the men folk. So many factors have been attributed to why female folk are not fully involved in the practice of journalism. Umar (2015) defines journalism as the occupation of reporting writing, editing, photographing or broadcasting news or of conducting any news organization as a business.

The word "journalism" according to Umar (2015) is derived from the word "journal" which implies a daily register or a diary or a book containing each day's business or transaction. Journalism as a profession is not limited to a particular gender. Rather, it is a profession that is seen as suitable for both men and woman (Ememyeonu, 1991). But most female prefer flamboyant roles in radio, television, advertising or public relations genres of journalism. This is where the idea of choice comes from for female graduates of mass communication in Nigeria.

Journalism is as media profession which offers a variety of career possibilities. In journalism, there are different career option opened to interested graduates to choose from. They include: Include: Photo journalism, news reporting, sports writing, investigative and interpretative journalism, freelancing or newspaper columns, news blogging, advertising and public relations etc. Aina (2004) distinguished some of the careers available in journalism: a reporter differentiates various career in journalism, stating that a reporter is a journalist who seeks out some information using researches and interviews. Whereas, investigative journalism requires a "keener news-sense" than the traditional reporting technique.

Ojomo (2008) described photo journalism as "telling a story with photographs-reporting with the aid of picture". Photo journalists are not ordinary photographers, they are professional photographers trained in the art of telling or reporting the news through the camera lens. In addition, we have sports presenters whose focus in all about reporting sporting automatics across the globe but nothing more. Same with political analysts, business analysts, health analysts, financial analysts and the new trend, the citizen journalism or news blogging news blogging is about using the internet network to report news activities and make it available to heterogonous audience as it happens through any form of social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp etc.

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Presently, almost all higher institutions of learning in Nigeria offer mass communication courses leading to the award of various degrees and certificates and well as diplomas at National and Higher levels up to Bachelor and Masters Degrees level. This is in a sharp contrast to what it used to be when candidates were reluctant to enroll in journalism as the preferred career choice as against courses such as Medicine, Accounting, Law and Architecture.

There is no doubt that journalism is a profession that needs both male and female gender. However, it has been observed that there are more female students studying mass communication than those practicing or aspiring to become journalists unlike their male counterparts. Various studies conducted across institutions offering journalism in Nigeria also indicate that there are more female students studying mass communication than their male counterparts. (Ali, 2010). Unfortunately, only a few of these female students follow through to make a career in journalism as it has been discovered that they prefer to have career in other areas of mass communication, such as public relations, advertising, broadcasting, photo-journalism, news casting, news blogging and publishing.

1.1.1. Career

The influence of career choice has a lasting impact on an individual. It serves to be a predictor and determinant of their prospective level of income, nature of work and consequently leaves a mark on the personality, demeanor and outlook of an individual. Thus, one wrong decision can change the fate of an individual. It is difficult for everyone to make a decision regarding their career. This individual action is manifested on a larger scale in the economic prosperity of a nation. Individuals who are misfits in their workplace tend to be less productive and efficient, and therefore are unable to achieve their goals.

The concept has been explained by Omeika (as cited in Jones and Larke, 2005), who defines occupation as a means of living, which has the power to change personalities, determine social status, predict expected earnings, determine social groups etc. Thus, its importance cannot be undermined. Given its complexity, it is then a point to ponder upon as to how career decisions are made. These are elucidated by Piaye (as cited in Alemu, 2013), who elaborates the importance of dialogue with peers, sessions with college counsellors, and discussions with parents and teachers on career selection as “career convention” or “career conference”. According to him “career convention is an instrument of career information”, and entails the following

- To create awareness regarding areas of interest and prospective career fields.
- To help in shortlisting preferable jobs.
- Provides opportunities in which parents, employees and career counsellors can exchange views.

A crucial influence in decision making regarding career is the home environment (James, 2000) as it lays the foundation of a child’s personality. It’s the parent’s upbringing which is the basis of the outcome of the personality. The values of the parents are transferred into the child. Besides the home, another major determinant of career choice is media. It provides exposure at the earliest stage. Media highlights social travails, global issues, trends and fashions, portrays the glamour of a culture, and the glitter of the consumer world. Moreover, talk shows, documentaries, movies and dramas portray careers such as law, media and advertising as very glamorous and appealing, thus drawing students towards them. Sometimes the choices of the peers also become a determining factor in choosing a profession. Other factors which influence career choice are family, parents, friends, culture, academic achievement, health factors, existing income level and financial constraints, media influences, prospective levels of income, employment opportunities, the social acceptability of profession, recognition, and work satisfaction among others. The purpose of this research was to investigate the various choices which have an influence on students’ career choice. It looked into the interplay of various decision-making influences on MS students’ chosen field. It sought answers to queries whether MS students chose their respective fields, had to reconcile with circumstances or had a say in the decisions. It gives an insight into the various factors which influence students’ decision making.

1.1.2. Public Relations Practice

Public Relation (PR) is the business of creating, sustaining and promoting good mental image for public and private organizations. It is a good career path someone who studied Mass Communication but doesn’t have taste for practicing traditional journalism. This career path can be trailed in two different forms. One has the option of working as an employee of the organization for which he practices PR. The other option is to work for PR firm to practice PR as consultant to other organizations.

Whichever way, PR practitioner will have to work hand-in-hand with journalists who are in the field. He would want to influence some positive media attention to his client. A challenging part of the PR is when one works as Crises Communication expert. This entails designing and executing the appropriate communication between the management and the employees of an organization in the time of crises.

Generally speaking, job growth projection in this career path is anticipated at 21% in 10 years between 2010 and 2020. Although this is the condition in USA, is being reflected across the globe. The Nigerian condition of economic growth is a positive sign for the same above average growth in PR career to be replicated.

In terms of salary, PR practitioners are among the highest earners among those who studied Mass Communication. Whereas those working directly in the PR units of private or public organizations earn up to \$54,940 annually, those working as consultants or as employees of PR firms earn up to \$77,010 (U.S. BLS, 2013).

Beyond the traditional journalism and PR practice, there are many other career paths that can be trailed with a great success. This includes career in Campaign Management, Independent Photojournalism, Press Secretary ship, Information Officer of an organization or a blogger.

Teaching journalism in the academe is though one of the noblest professions, it is arguably one of the most tasking and least paying jobs with degrees in Mass Communication. This explains why there is dearth academic human resource in Mass Communication field around the globe. Very few people are interested in spending seven more years in the university and additional thousands of dollars only to earn less. What is likely to compensate is winning research grants and competition within which is stiffer than imaginable.

1.2. Theoretical Framework

According to McQuail (2007), theory is a general proposition, it is based on observation and logical argument that states the relationship between observed phenomenon and seeks either to explain or predict the relations. Theoretical framework on its own is the conscious and deliberate decision that a researcher has made in terms of theory or combination of theories, which guide his research effort. The theories to be used for this study are the perception and social cognitive theory. The validity of this study is solely hinged on these theories and shall form the base of the study.

1.2.1. Perception Theory

The perception theory is an account of attitude change developed by psychologist Daryl Bem. It asserts that people develop their attitudes by observing their behaviour and concluding what attitudes must have caused them. The theory is counterintuitive in nature, as the conventional wisdom is that attitude comes prior to behaviours. Furthermore, the theory suggests that a person induces attitudes without accessing internal cognition and mood states. The person reasons their own overt behaviours rationally in the same way they attempt to explain others' behaviours. The issue of perception or image is so complex that it has to be analysed within a fitting theoretical framework. This is so because there is a strong likelihood that individuals have different perceptions of objects. According to Huffman and Vernoy (2000), perception is the process of selecting, organizing, and interpreting sensory data into useable mental representation of the world. On the other hand, according to Worchel and Shebilske (1989), perception is the process of interpreting information.

Besides, Szilagyi and Wallace defined perception as a process by which individuals attend to incoming stimuli, organize, and interpret such stimuli into message that in turn indicate an appropriate action or behavior. Thus, perception is an action in which someone gives the stimulus and response about something which happens in the reality. Although some people are facing a similar object, they may have a different perception about it. It is because everyone has their own experience in the past. There are many experts that describe the relation between the people's experience and perception. Mouly (1973) stated that two persons looking at the same phenomenon may see very different things. Wick and Pick also stated that there is a connection between perception and experience. According to Slameto, perception is the process by which a message or information concerning the entry into the human brain. Through continuous human perception, held a relationship with its environment. This connection is done via the senses, such as sensory-viewer, listen, touch, and taste. This theory is relevant to this study because it explains how JABU and ACE students perceive journalism as a career and how their choice is shaped by such perception.

1.2.2. Social Cognitive Theory

The study also adopted social cognitive theory. The theory was propounded by Philip and Ziller (1992). Only social category theory has been observed to have similar modes of orientation and behaving which relate people in the same social category to such phenomena as mass communication in similar ways. The theory posits that "members of contemporary urban-industrial societies could be structured into social categories based on common characteristics into social categories based on common characteristics like social class, religion ethnic identity and rural residence, and that such categorization has implementations for mass communication message". According to Ibraheem (2018) in Aina (2003), its origin stems from the need of advertisers for specialized audiences. It is assumed that the categories to which individuals belong provide them with similar frame of reference and cognition.

Agbo, Ojobor and Ezinwa (2008) also stressed that "members of a particular social category will select more or less similar communication content and will respond to it roughly in equal way". Therefore, most female mass communication students, who belong to the same social category in the society, develop negative attitudes towards journalism as a career. As most of the female communicators are negatively affected by the discriminations from the society and their families, it implies that they have responded to the idea of not accepting the choice of journalism as a career.

2. Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

The study aimed to examine the attitude of mass communication trainees of Joseph Ayo Babalola University (JABU) and Adeyemi college of Education (ACE) towards journalism as a career. The researcher adopted purposive sampling technique and as a result; a total number of 347 respondents filled the questionnaire 110 (JABU Mass communication trainees) and 237 (ACE Mass communication trainees). The data were presented in frequency and percentage distribution of the different categories of variables that were displayed in the table.

2.1. Demographic Information

Table 1 The gender of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	161	46.4
Female	186	53.6
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 1 above shows that 161 (representing 46.4%) of the respondents are male while 186 (representing 53.6%) of the respondents are female. Data above shows that majority of the respondents for this study is female, and that the data were significantly fairly distributed between the two genders.

Figure 1 Bar Chart showing sex distribution of the respondents

Table 2 The age bracket of the respondents

Age bracket	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18 - 30	256	73.8
30 - 40	71	20.4
40 above	20	5.8
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 2 reveals that out of the total number of the respondents, 256 (representing 73.8%) of the Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU were between age 18-30, 71 (representing 18.2%) were between age 30 - 40 while 20 (representing 5.8%) of the respondents were aged 40 and above.

From the analysis presented in Table 2 above, it was discovered that majority of the respondents were between the ages 15-25.

Figure 2 Bar Chart showing age distribution of the respondents

Table 3 The institution of respondents

Name of institution	Frequency	Percentage (%)
AAUA	237	68.3
JABU	110	31.7
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 3 above shows that 237 (representing 68.3%) of the respondents are Mass Communication trainees of Adeyemi college of Education (ACE), while 110 (representing 31.7%) of the respondents are Mass communication trainees of Joseph Ayo Babalola University (JABU).

Analysis above shows that majority of the respondents are Mass Communication trainees of Adeyemi College of Education (ACE).

Table 4 The level of respondents

Level of respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)
100	37	10.6
200	67	19.2
300	108	31.1
400	135	39.1
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 4 above shows that 37 (representing 10.6%) of the respondents are in 100 level, 67 (representing 19.2%) are in 200 level, 108 (representing 31.1%) are in 300 level, and 135 (representing 39.1%) are in 400 level. The analysis in the

table above shows that most of the respondents for this study are 400 level Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU.

2.1.1. Data presentation on the various attitudes of Mass Communication trainees of JABU and ACE towards journalism as a career?

This aims to ascertain the various attitudes of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU towards journalism as a career. Items 1 to 5 from the structured questionnaire were used to answer this question; responses to each item on the questionnaire are therefore presented in tables 5-9 below.

Table 5 If respondents like journalism

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	193	55.3
No	155	44.7
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Data from the table 5 above shows that 193(representing 55.3%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU says they like Journalism, while 155(representing 44.7%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU says they don't like Journalism. The data presented above reveals that majority of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU like Journalism.

Table 6 The reason respondents are studying Mass Communication as a course

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Personal decision	169	48.7
The institution gave me the course	92	26.5
Parents/guardians factor	86	24.8
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

In table 6 above, data shows that 169(representing 48.7%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU says they are studying Mass Communication as a course because they desire to study mass communication, 92(representing 26.5%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU says they studying Mass Communication as a course because the institution of study gave them the course, and 86(representing 24.8%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU says they are studying Mass Communication as a course because their parents/guardians made them to study the course. The data presented above shows that majority of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU are studying mass communication because of their personal decision to study the course, while few are because of parent/guardian's factor.

Table 7 If respondents will you choose journalism as a career

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	158	45.5
No	189	54.5
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

Data from the table 7 above shows that 158(representing 45.5%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU says they like Journalism as a career, while 189(representing 54.5%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU

says they don't like Journalism as a career. The data presented above reveals that majority of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU don not like Journalism as a career.

Table 8 The aspect of journalism preferable to respondents

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
News writing/reporting	59	17.0
News casting	94	27.1
On-Air-Personality (OAP)	106	30.5
News blogging/online media	69	19.9
Investigative journalism	19	5.5
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Data from table 8 above show that 59 respondents (representing 17.0%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU says they prefer the news writing/reporting aspect of journalism, 94(representing 27.1%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU say that they prefer the news casting aspect of journalism, 106 respondents (representing 30.5%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU say they prefer the On-Air-Personality (OAP) aspect of journalism, 69(representing 19.9%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU says that they prefer news blogging/online media aspect of journalism, and 19 respondents (representing 5.5%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU say they prefer investigative journalism aspect of journalism.

It can be deduced from the data presented above that Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU prefers the aspect of journalism in this order; On-Air-personality, news casting, news blogging/online media, news writing/ reporting and the less preferred is investigative journalism.

Table 9 Respondents view on if Journalism as a profession is gender biased

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	63	18.2
Agree	61	17.6
Disagree	90	25.9
Strongly disagree	115	33.1
Undecided	18	5.2
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

In data 9 above, data show that 63(18.2%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly agree that journalism as a profession is gender biased, 61(representing 17.6) agree to the same motion, while 90(representing 25.9%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU disagree that journalism as a career is gender biased, 115(representing 33.1%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly disagree that journalism as a career is gender biased and 18(representing 5.2%) were undecided.

The data presented above reveal that Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU have a positive attitude towards journalism as a career as majority of them sees journalism as an unbiased profession.

2.1.2. Data presentation on the prospects and challenges of Mass Communication trainees of JABU and ACE towards journalism as a study/career?

This seeks to ascertain the prospects as well as the challenges of Mass Communication trainees of JABU and ACE towards journalism as a study and career. Items 6 to 14 from the structured questionnaire were used to answer this question; responses to each item on the questionnaire are therefore presented in tables 10-19 below.

Table 10 Respondents view on if Journalism as a career comes with fame

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	135	38.9
Agree	102	29.5
Disagree	50	14.4
Strongly disagree	47	13.5
Undecided	13	3.7
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

In table 10 above, data show that 135(38.9%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly agree that journalism as a career comes with fame, 102(representing 29.5) agree to the same motion, while 50(representing 14.4%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU disagree that journalism as a career comes with fame, 47(representing 13.5%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly disagree that journalism as a career comes with fame and 13(representing 3.7%) were undecided. From the data presented above, it can be deduced that Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU sees journalism as a career that comes with fame.

Table 11 Respondents view on if Journalism as a career brings about financial stability

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	35	10.1
Agree	82	23.5
Disagree	70	20.2
Strongly disagree	147	42.2
Undecided	13	4.0
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

In table 11 above, data show that 35(10.1%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly agree that journalism as a career brings about financial stability, 82(representing 23.5) agree to the same motion, while 70(representing 20.2%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU disagree that journalism as a career brings about financial stability, 147(representing 42.2%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly disagree that journalism as a career brings about financial stability and 13(representing 4.0%) were undecided. The data presented above show that Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU have a negative attitude about journalism with their opinion that journalism as a career does not bring about financial stability. This can be deduced to be one of the challenges of journalism as a career.

Table 12 Respondents view on if Journalism as a career places you among the greats in the society

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	87	25.1
Agree	122	35.1
Disagree	70	20.2
Strongly disagree	45	13.0
Undecided	23	6.6
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

In table 12 above, data show that 87(25.1%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly agree that journalism as a career places you among the greats in the society, 122(representing 35.1) agree to the same motion, while 70(representing 20.2%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU disagree that journalism as a career places you among the greats in the society, 45(representing 13.0%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly disagree that journalism as a career places you among the greats in the society and 23(representing 6.6%) were undecided. The data presented above reveal that Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU opined that journalism as a career places you among the greats in the society. This can be deduced to be one of the prospects of journalism as a career.

Table 13 If respondents have adequate practical facilities for studying mass communication in school

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	58	16.7
Agree	61	17.6
Disagree	130	37.5
Strongly disagree	67	19.3
Undecided	31	8.9
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

In table 13 above, data show that 58(16.7%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly agree that there are adequate practical facilities for studying Mass Communication in their school, 61(representing 17.6) agree to the same motion, while 130(representing 37.5%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU disagree that there are no adequate practical facilities for studying Mass Communication in their school, 67(representing 19.3%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly disagree that there are no adequate practical facilities for studying Mass Communication in their school and 31(representing 8.9%) were undecided. The data presented above shows that that there are no adequate practical facilities for studying Mass Communication in their schools.

Table 14 Respondents view on if a career journalist faces intimidation

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	100	28.8
Agree	141	40.6
Disagree	50	14.4
Strongly disagree	45	13.0
Undecided	11	3.2
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

In table 14 above, data show that 100(28.8%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly agree that career journalists face intimidation, 141(representing 40.6) agree to the same motion, while 50(representing 14.4%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU disagree that career journalists face intimidation, 45(representing 13.0%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly disagree that career journalists face intimidation and 11(representing 3.2%) were undecided. The data presented above revealed that career journalists face intimidation.

Table 15 Respondents view on if a career journalist faces abuse in the line of duty

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	107	30.8
Agree	143	41.2
Disagree	44	12.7
Strongly disagree	43	12.4
Undecided	10	2.9
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

In table 15 above, data show that 107(30.8%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly agree that career journalists face abuse in the line of duty, 143(representing 41.2) agree to the same motion, while 44(representing 12.7%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU disagree that career journalists face abuse in the line of duty, 43(representing 12.4%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly disagree that career journalists faces abuse in the line of duty and 10(representing 2.9%) were undecided. The data presented above show that career journalists face abuse in the line of duty.

Table 16 Respondents view on if a career journalist gets low income

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	67	19.3
Agree	74	21.3
Disagree	100	28.8
Strongly disagree	61	17.6
Undecided	45	13.0
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

In table 16 above, data show that 67(19.3%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly agree that career journalists get low income, 74(representing 21.3) agree to the same motion, while 100(representing 28.8%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU disagree that career journalists get low income, 61(representing 17.6%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly disagree that career journalists get low income and 45(representing 13.0%) were undecided. The data presented above shows that career journalists do not get low income.

2.1.3. Data Presentation on the Expectations of Mass Communication Trainees of JABU and ACE towards Choosing Journalism as a Study/Career?

This research question seeks to ascertain the expectations of Mass Communication trainees of JABU and ACE towards choosing journalism as a study/career. Item 15 to 17 from the structured questionnaire will be used to answer this question; responses to each item on the questionnaire are therefore presented in tables 20-23 below:

Table 17 Respondents view on if there should be more practical oriented courses while studying mass communication

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	178	51.3
Agree	123	35.4
Disagree	20	5.8
Strongly disagree	21	6.1
Undecided	5	1.4
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

In table 17 above, data show that 178(51.3%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly agree that there should be more practical oriented courses while studying mass communication, 123(representing 35.4) agree to the same motion, while 20(representing 5.8%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU disagree there should be more practical oriented courses while studying mass communication, 21(representing 6.1%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly disagree there should be more practical oriented courses while studying mass communication and 5(representing 1.4%) were undecided. The data presented above reveals that majority of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU opine that there should be more practical oriented courses while studying mass communication.

Table 18 Respondents view on if there should more protection of journalists against abuse and intimidation

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	193	55.6
Agree	139	40.1
Disagree	6	1.7
Strongly disagree	4	1.2
Undecided	5	1.4
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

In table 18 above, data show that 193(55.6%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly agree that there should be more protection of journalists against abuse and intimidation, 139(representing 40.1) agree to the same motion, while 6(representing 1.7%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU disagree there should be more protection of journalists against abuse and intimidation, 4(representing 1.2%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly disagree that there be should more protection of journalists against abuse and intimidation and 5(representing 1.4%) were undecided. The data presented above reveal that majority of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU opines that there should be more protection of journalists against abuse and intimidation.

Table 19 Respondents view on if professional journalists should be treated and accorded the same relevance like their contemporaries in the medical field

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	200	57.6
Agree	110	31.7
Disagree	18	5.2
Strongly disagree	14	4.0
Undecided	5	1.4
Total	347	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

In table 19 above, data show that 200(57.6%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly agree that Professional journalists should be treated and accorded the same relevance like their contemporaries in the medical field, 110(representing 31.7) agree to the same motion, while 18(representing 5.2%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU disagree that professional journalists should be treated and accorded the same relevance like their contemporaries in the medical field, 14(representing 4.0%) of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU strongly disagree that Professional journalists should be treated and accorded the same relevance like their contemporaries in the medical field and 5(representing 1.4%) were undecided. The data presented above reveals that Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU opine that professional journalists should be treated and accorded the same relevance like their contemporaries in the medical field

Table 20 Expectations of respondents towards journalism as a career

Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU expectations towards journalism as a career	Themed responses
	Journalists should be paid more Journalists should be protected from intimidation and harassment More respects and recognition should be accorded to journalists Government should not interfere in the activities of journalists. Career journalists should discharge their duties without fear or favour.

Source: Field survey, 2025

Data in table 20 above show that Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU opined the following as their expectations towards journalism as a career; Journalists should be paid more, Journalists should be protected from intimidation and harassment, more respects and recognition should be accorded to journalists, government should not interfere in the activities of journalists, and career journalists should discharge their duties without fear or favor.

3. Discussion of Findings

It was discovered in this study that there are more female student studying mass communication as a course than their male counterparts. This aligns with Ali (2010) assertion that journalism is a profession that needs both male and female gender. However, it has been observed that there are more female students studying mass communication than those practicing or aspiring to become journalists unlike their male counterparts. Various studies conducted across institutions offering journalism in Nigeria also indicate that there are more female students studying mass communication than their male counterparts. Unfortunately, only a few of these female students intend to make a career in journalism as it has been discovered that they prefer to have career in other areas of mass communication, such as public relations, advertizing, broadcasting, photo-journalism, news casting, news blogging and publishing.

To ascertain the various attitudes of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU towards journalism as a career, it was found out in the study that majority of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU like journalism, and most of the trainees are studying mass communication because of their personal decision to study the course, while few are because of parent/guardians factor. This corroborates Suutari (2003) reports that several studies have indicated a positive relationship between interests and career choice.

It was found out that majority of Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU do not like journalism as a career, corroborating this finding, a study carried out by Ali (2010) to find out the attitude of mass communication student towards journalism as a career, there's a general belief that although a very large number of graduates of journalism are produced from different higher institutions in Nigeria, whereas, only few of them actually practice journalism as a career. Findings revealed that mass communication students have a negative attitude towards journalism as a career.

Mass Communication trainee of ACE and JABU prefers the aspect of journalism in this order; On-Air-personality, news casting, news blogging/online media, news writing/ reporting and the less preferred is investigative journalism. Study

also revealed that Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU have a positive attitude towards journalism as a career as majority of them sees journalism as an unbiased profession.

In a bid to ascertain the prospects as well as the challenges of Mass Communication trainees of JABU and ACE towards journalism as a study and career, it was discovered in the study that some of the prospects of journalism as a career is the fame that comes with it, journalism as a career places you among the greats in the society,

It was found out that Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU have a negative attitude about journalism with their opinion that journalism as a career does not bring about financial stability, that career journalists' faces intimidation, career journalists face abuse in the line of duty, career journalists do not get low income. This can be deduced to be one of the challenges of journalism as a career. Also, it was discovered that there are no adequate practical facilities for studying Mass Communication in their schools.

Furthermore, to ascertain the expectations of Mass Communication trainees of JABU and ACE towards choosing journalism as a study/career, study found out that Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU opine that there should be more practical oriented courses while studying mass communication.

It was also discovered that Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU opine that there should be more protection of journalists against abuse and intimidation, Professional journalists should be treated and accorded the same relevance like their contemporaries in the medical field.

Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU opined the following as their expectations towards journalism as a career; Journalists should be paid more, journalists should be protected from intimidation and harassment, More respects and recognition should be accorded to journalists, government should not interfere in the activities of journalists, and Career journalists should discharge their duties without fear or favor.

4. Conclusion

From the findings of this study, the researcher is able to conclude that

Mass communication trainees chose to study the course due to their personal decision but majority of them do not want to choose journalism as a career and Mass Communication trainee of ACE and JABU prefer the aspect of journalism in this order; On-Air-personality, news casting, news blogging/online media, news writing/ reporting and the less preferred is investigative journalism. Mass communication students have a negative attitude towards journalism as a career.

Also, it can be concluded that some of the prospects of journalism as a career is the fame that comes with it, journalism as a career places you among the greats in the society. Mass Communication trainees of ACE and JABU have a negative attitude about journalism with their opinion that journalism as a career does not bring about financial stability, that career journalists' faces intimidation, career journalists face abuse in the line of duty, career journalists do not get low income. This can be deduced to be one of the challenges of journalism as a career. Also, there are no adequate practical facilities for studying Mass Communication in their schools.

The expectations of Mass Communication trainees of JABU and ACE towards choosing journalism as a study/career, is that there should be more practical oriented courses while studying mass communication, and there should be more protection of journalists against abuse and intimidation, professional journalists should be treated and accorded the same relevance like their contemporaries in the medical field.

Compliance with ethical standards

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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